

Dirac Equation form $-Et+px$? Part II

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In Part I, we suggested that since $A=-Et+px$ implies degenerate A values for $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ and $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$, one may create a function $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which creates these degenerate points, but has a modulus of 1. We then suggested that one may use $\partial/\partial t$ partial and $\partial/\partial x$ partial in place of p and E to obtain the values of E and p in a linear equation linking E, p, m_0 . We also suggested that one may use $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, together with $\partial/\partial t$ partial and $\partial/\partial x$ partial in $-EE+pp=m_0^2$.

Here, we wish to start with $P(x)=1$, together with the degeneracy \hbar/p and argue that one requires at least two real positive probability functions to achieve this and also capture the information of periodicity (i.e. degenerate x points). At this point there is no complex $\exp(ipx)$, but we argue that it may be formed from $P(x)=1$ using $P(x)=F_1(x)+1-F_1(x)$ and writing this as a product of $\exp(ig(x))\exp(-ig(x))$ with $g(x)=bx$ being the simplest solution. This is linked to conservation of b , which turns out to be p , momentum. $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-\partial/\partial x$, but the question becomes: Why does one need a square root function (so to speak) of $P(x)$ in the first place? What necessity is there to have an eigenfunction of p , while still displaying periodicity. Note: $F_1(x)$ and $1-F_1(x)$ are both positive, real and show periodicity. They are not eigenfunctions of p . The problem with only using $P(x)=1$ is that one has $-EE+pp=m_0^2$ which does not display periodicity. One needs to associate this with a function which does and that means making E and p operators which bring back E and p as eigenvalues. In short, we argue that the taking of the square root of $P(x)=1$ can be thought of as following from linking periodicity (degenerate x and t points) to eigenvalues E and p which appear in equations. It is not simply that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is convenient for picking off E and p values, but that as eigenfunctions of spatial and temporal translations, it displays invariance in space as well as conservation. In particular, $P(x)$ has no direction (because it describes a static distribution) and so does not describe dynamics fully.

$P(x)=1$ and Periodicity

In previous notes, we argued that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ leads to degenerate x and t points:

$$x=x_0+n\hbar/p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad t=t_0+n\hbar/E \quad ((1b)) \quad \text{with } n=\text{integer}$$

In other words, there is both periodicity yet also the notion of $P(x)=1$. The question then becomes: How does one describe this using classical probability. It seems that $P(x)$ must be the sum of two classical probabilities $F_1(x) > 0$ and $1-F_1(x) > 0$, both real functions, i.e.

$$P(x) = F_1(x) + 1-F_1(x) \quad ((2))$$

These represent two mutually exclusive probabilities in the classical sense with both having the periodicity of $n\hbar/p$. I.e.

$$F1(x+n\hbar/p) = F1(x) \quad ((3))$$

As a result, one may describe $P(x)=1$ as being linked to two mutually exclusive classical probability events. There is no need for $\exp(ipx)$ at this point.

Given that ((2)) is the sum of two positive numbers, it may be written as:

$$P(x) = \{ \sqrt{F1} + i \sqrt{1-F1} \} \{ \sqrt{F1} - i \sqrt{1-F1} \} \quad ((4))$$

$$P(x) = r \exp(i g(x)) \exp(-ig(x)) = 1 \quad \text{so } r=1 \quad ((5))$$

$$g(x+n/p) = g(x) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{The next thing to note is that: } dP(x)/dx = 0 \quad \text{so } d/dx (\exp(i g(x)) \exp(-ig(x))) = 0. \quad ((7))$$

The simplest way to have a function periodic in $1/p$ satisfying ((7)) is to have $\exp(ipx)$. We note that this is immediately linked to conservation of p because $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$.

$\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$. The point we wish to make in this note is that even though $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution and an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$, it is not at all clear why one should make use of this. In other words, one might dismiss this as a mathematical curiosity. ((2)) already captures $P(x)=1$ and periodicity of $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$. Why is $\exp(px)$ required? This function is complex and acts as a kind of square root of classical probability which is not something that one traditionally uses in classical probability.

We argue that the reason for taking $\exp(ipx)$ seriously in this discussion is its direct link to E and p . In other words, given the Lorentz invariant:

$$-EE + pp = \text{momo} \quad ((8))$$

there is no information about the degenerate x and t points, even though they exist. One might wish to extend ((8)) to not only show a relationship between E, p, mo , but to also indicate the degeneracy. The degeneracy may be introduced by hand through $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, as this form allows one to easily "pick off" E and p using id/dt partial and $-id/dx$ partial. Using $F1(x)$ and $1-F1(x)$ does not allow one to easily obtain E and p . Thus, the reason in this discussion for keeping (not rejecting) $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is its direct link to the values E and p which appear in equations. In other words, it is only through the square root of $P(x)=1$ that one may obtain access to the E and p values required and still maintain periodicity due to degenerate x and t points. There should, however, be a more fundamental reason.

Invariance of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

Above, we argued that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ was convenient for picking off E and p , but it seems that there is a more important reason for its use. The operators $\partial/\partial t$ and $\partial/\partial x$ are linked to generators of translation in t and x and $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ being an eigenfunction mathematically displays this invariance directly whereas $F_1(x)$ and $1-F_1(x)$ do not. This invariance is directly linked with conservation of momentum which we discussed above. Thus, there seem to be important physical and mathematical reasons for retaining $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

In other words, $dP(x)/dx=1$ is really the combination of $d/dx \exp(ipx)$ and $d/dx \exp(-ipx)$ in $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ which demonstrates invariance in both directions. Thus, $P(x)$ really describes static objects as we have suggested in previous notes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one only wishes to demonstrate $P(x)=1$ and periodicity due to degenerate $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ and $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ (which follow from $A=-Et+px$), then there is no reason to consider $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. It suffices to introduce two real, positive functions $F_1(x)$ and $1-F_1(x)$ such that their sum is $P(x)=1$. Mathematically, one may write this as: $P(x)=\exp(ig(x))\exp(-ig(x))$ where $g(x)$ is periodic with $g(x)=g(x+n/p)$. The simplest solution is $\exp(ipx)$, but this is complex and at first glance, it seems that there is no reason to retain it. Its usefulness seems to occur in that it is an eigenfunction of $\partial/\partial t$ and $\partial/\partial x$ making it simple to "pick off" E and p values which appear in equations such as $-E^2+pp=m^2$. This equation does not display the full information of degenerate x and t points and so one needs to bring over functions which do, but this means that E and p become operators. Bringing in $F_1(x)$ and $1-F_1(x)$ does not allow one to easily obtain p and E , whereas $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ does. Such a reason, however, is not enough for retaining $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. We argue that d/dx and d/dt are generators of translations in space and time and the eigenfunction $\exp(-iEt)\exp(-ipx)$ demonstrates this invariance which is also directly linked to conservation of E and p . The classical probability functions $F_1(x)$ and $1-F_1(x)$ cannot do this and so they are rejected in favor of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, which interestingly is like a square root of a classical probability $P(x)=1$.